

Self-consistent Methods in Hückel and Extended Hückel Theories. Part-VI. A Logical Analysis of Optimisable Parameters

AJAY K. BARAL,

Department of Chemistry, Narasingha Dutt College, Howrah-711 101

AJOY K. MUKHOPADHYAY

Department of Chemistry, Uluberia College, Uluberia

and

NIRAD G. MUKHERJEE*

Department of Chemistry, University College of Science, Calcutta-700 009

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A logical analysis of the parameters used in the extended Hückel method has been made to show their transferability. A self-consistent extended Hückel method developed earlier has been used at first for calculation of some molecular properties of some simple diatomics to establish the point and then the method has been put to a more stringent test by considering some anesthetically important halo-substituted hydrocarbons.

FROM the inception of Extended Hückel theory¹, a large volume of work has been done by several authors^{2-4,6,7}. However, the lack of theoretical justifiability for the newly developed iterative procedures^{3,4,6} was first pointed out by Harris⁵.

A self-consistent procedure for the Hückel and Extended Hückel theories, following Harris' proposal, was first fully developed by us earlier⁸ and a method of solution was also suggested. The procedure was later successfully applied to quite a few representative unsaturated⁹ and saturated molecules^{10,11} for studying some important properties. The procedure has recently been extended to include a formal perturbation¹². The prime motive of the present paper is to make a study of the parameters used in the Extended Hückel theory and make a logical analysis of the situation. Such an analysis becomes all the more necessary because of the fact that though often criticised for its poor results, the method is still in very much use for big molecules¹³⁻¹⁷. In order to analyse the situation we suggest no new parameters. The parameters used in previous calculations have been retained. A test calculation on some simple diatomics has been made to show the dependence of parameters on the electronic environment. The choice of these molecules is largely dictated by the fact that these molecules are simple without any geometrical symmetry and hence cancellation of errors by factors other than electronic can suitably be avoided.

The parameters :

One of the elegances of a semi-empirical theory like the Extended Hückel or any of the variations

of the ZDO approximation is the transferability of the parameters. In any new semi-empirical approach or in any modification of any of these methods this elegance should not be destroyed unless theoretical justification goes to the contrary. But one must understand why and under what circumstances such transferability is possible. We judge the two parameters, namely ω and K , used in the self-consistent Hückel and Extended Hückel theories from this angle.

ω -values : This parameter introduced first by Wheland and Mann¹³ has been extensively used by Streitwieser¹⁴. A constant value of $\omega = 1.4$ has been mostly used. Since, our method utilises the principle of omega-technique extending its applicability to EHT, it is worthwhile to see whether there exists any theoretical justification or computational analyses in favour of this accepted value. We recall that the Hückel theory, in spite of its crudeness, is still considered to be satisfactory, at least qualitatively, for simple conjugated hydrocarbons. This is because of the fact that it considers π -electrons in a framework of environmental symmetry. Therefore, the parameters should not depend on the particular molecule but it should depend on the environment in which a particular atom is placed in a molecule. This is quite important as it can change the value of electronic integrals. The environment created by a less electronegative element will not be the same as that created by a more electronegative element. So we can expect a dependence of the parameter on the electronegativity of elements though it may not be possible to give a closed analytical expression for

this functional dependence. It is quite interesting to observe that the change of ω -values corresponds closely with the change in electronegativity for different atoms. With a view to studying explicitly the dependence between these two, i.e. ω and the electronegativity, we have estimated ω -values for different elements in the following way. We first fix the value for hydrogen and carbon by simultaneous variation of ω -values for a system like CH_4 . Values for other elements are then fixed successively by considering systems like NH_3 , HCN , HCHO , H_2O , CH_3F , BN etc. When we plot ω -value against the electronegativity a parabolic curve is obtained†. We find in Table 1 that $\omega_{\text{H}}=2.5$ and $\omega_{\text{F}}=0.3$. All other ω -values lie within these two extremes and on the parabola. It is interesting to note that the average of these two extremes is 1.4, a value which has been used by many workers mainly for the pi-electrons in carbon systems.

 TABLE 1—VALUES OF ω AND ELECTRONEGATIVITY

Element	ω values	Electro- negativity*
Fluorine	-0.3	4.0
Oxygen	-0.5	3.5
Nitrogen	-0.6	3.0
Carbon	-0.7	2.5
Boron	-1.5	2.0
Hydrogen	-2.5	2.1

*C. A. Coulson, "Valence", Oxford University Press, Oxford, 1961, p. 140.

With these values of ω we calculate some properties of compounds other than those which were used for parametrisation. The results, discussed later, corroborate our view that ω -values are different for different elements and these are transferable irrespective of the molecule. In all these and later calculations, a value of 1.75 was used for K for the reason given in the next section.

Choice of K: If one considers the one-electron operator (self-consistent or not) as a simple multiplier (unity) and ignores all interactions, it is seen that an off-diagonal element of the operator in a non-orthogonal basis can be approximated as a mean, which may be arithmetical, geometric or harmonic, of the two corresponding diagonal elements times the overlap. As the harmonic mean involve reciprocal relationship, this can be dispensed with. Thus

$$H_{ij}=0.5 S_{ij} (H_{ii}+H_{jj}) \quad (1a)$$

$$\text{or, } H_{ij}=S_{ij} \sqrt{H_{ii} \cdot H_{jj}} \quad (1b)$$

H_{ii} and H_{jj} being proportional to charges, the magnitude of H_{ij} is largely determined by the overlap S_{ij} . When the one-electron operator is not a unit operator or we include electronic interaction, the above expressions are not strictly valid but we may assume that they still remain approximately propor-

tional to the above averages. So the expressions (1a) and (1b) are modified to

$$H_{ij}=0.5 K S_{ij} (H_{ii}+H_{jj}) \quad (2a)$$

$$\text{or, } H_{ij}=K S_{ij} \sqrt{H_{ii} \cdot H_{jj}} \quad (2b)$$

where K is an adjustable parameter (2a) in the widely used Wolfsberg-Helmholtz¹⁸ expression. Both (2a) and (2b) have been used in EHT and other semi-empirical calculations. It is difficult to say which one should give a more realistic approximation. From the point of view of automatic choice of the signs of the integrals, the choice of (2a) seems preferable and this has been widely used in the literature. The most commonly used value of K is 1.75. With $K=1.75$ we can rewrite (2a) as

$$H_{ij}=0.5 S_{ij} (H_{ii}+H_{jj})+0.5 \times 0.75 S_{ij} (H_{ii}+H_{jj}) \quad (3)$$

The first part is just the arithmetic mean and the second part may be considered due to the electronic interaction. Once we have written the expression in the above way we find a similarity of the expression with the semi-theoretical expression of bond parameter by Bhattacharyya and Chowdhury¹⁹ where a value of 0.75 was considered as the best value for the constant in the second part of this expression. So in our opinion, $K=1.75$ should be a good value and obtain transferability as in Bhattacharyya and Chowdhury's case.

Results and Discussion

Once we have fixed the ω -values for different elements and decided upon our choice of K we use this for the calculation of ionisation energies etc. for a few simple systems already specified.

Table 2 gives the values of the ionisation potentials, dipole moments and dissociation energies of some diatomics. All the calculations except Li have been made with optimised values of ω . Since each Li atom contributes one electron (although it is a highly electropositive metal) one may crudely assume the situation almost similar to a π -electron system and use the average value of 1.4 for it. The ionisation potential values are remarkably well within allowable errors of experiment. These values can claim precision to almost of same degree with the values obtained by CNDO. For LiH, the calculated values differ considerably from the experimental values. This has to be for reason just mentioned above. The CNDO values also differ to a considerable extent. The dissociation energies are also compared with the values obtained by Politzer *et al.*⁷ where these are available. Except for nitrogen molecule where it is non-polar, all other values are less than the experimental values. These molecules are definitely polar.

Table 3 shows the internuclear bond distances and the results has been compared with those obtained by CNDO and experiment. Consistently good and encouraging results have been obtained for the molecules. These results are not only comparable with sophisticated methods like CNDO,

† The reproduction of the plot has been avoided for facility of publication; xerox copies of the plot may be had of the authors.

TABLE 2—IONISATION POTENTIAL, DIPOLE MOMENT AND DISSOCIATION ENERGY

Molecule	Ionisation potentials (eV)			Dipole moments (Debye)			Dissociation energy (eV)		
	Present method	CNDO*	Exptl.*	Present method	CNDO*	Exptl.*	Present method	Poltzers method**	Exptl.**
N ₂	15.8	18.51	15.58	0	0	0	12.5	8.87	9.76
CO	10.61	17.54	14.013	4.05	0.64	0.112	6.87	7.5	11.09
BF	11.9	14.59	13.24 (INDO)	6.69	1.37	1.04 (SCF)	2.6	4.01	7.85
LiF	12.21	11.97	11.67 (INDO)	8.13	7.9	6.6	2.12	3.48	5.95
HF	15.54	21.14	15.77	2.44	1.86	1.82			
LiH	13.93	13.21	6.5	6.38	6.16	5.88			
BH	13.69	13.02 (INDO)	9.7	2.91	2.13	1.84			
BN	11.821	12.89	13.38 (INDO)	0.31	0.36	0.50			

*J. A. Pople and D. L. Beveridge, "Approximate Molecular Orbital Theory", McGraw-Hill, New York, 1970.
 **Ref. 7.

INDO, etc., but also sometimes are very close to the experimental values.

are available. This, we think, tells much in favour of the SC EHT method.

TABLE 3—BOND DISTANCE (Å)

Molecule	Present	CNDO*	INDO*	Observe*
N ₂	1.151	1.140	1.147	1.094
CO	1.220	1.191	1.195	1.128
BF	1.564	1.404	1.408	1.262
LiF	2.247	2.161	2.162	1.51
HF	1.082	1.0	1.006	0.917
LiH	1.513	1.573	1.572	1.595
BH	1.098	1.194	1.204	1.233
BN	1.276	1.268	1.269	1.281

*J. A. Pople and D. L. Beveridge, "Approximate Molecular Orbital Theory", New York, 1970.

Our analysis shows that it is not necessary to search for better values of optimisable parameters. When chosen properly, they retain the property of transferability.

Now in order to put a more stringent test to our procedure we consider below a few halosubstituted aliphatic hydrocarbons. Moreover, these compounds offer a special interest for their use as general anesthetics. All these have at least one 'acidic hydrogen' and the primary dependence of the anesthetic property on the electron distribution is established by the fact that these molecules with similar ground state conformations show difference in activity. In the calculation we have used the standard tetrahedral geometry for the carbon atoms and the standard bond lengths for all the bonds.

In Tables 4 and 5 we present the ionisation potentials and the dipole moments respectively, of the substituted hydrocarbons calculated by the conventional EHT method along with those calculated by the method developed by us. These are then compared with the values obtained from CNDO calculations wherever they are available. The experimental values are collected in the last columns. For the ionisation potentials results show that our results are quite comparable to the CNDO values and in some cases even better than the CNDO values and nearer to the experimental values wherever they

TABLE 4—IONISATION POTENTIAL (eV)

Molecule	EHT	Present method	CNDO*	Exptl.** value
CH ₃ F	14.97	12.72	12.87	12.54
CH ₂ F ₂	14.54	12.63	12.43	12.72
CH ₃ F	15.54	13.72	13.12	13.8
CF ₄	17.62	15.21	15.42	15.35
CH ₃ -CH ₂ -F	13.84	11.05	—	—
CH ₃ -CHF ₂	13.63	11.21	—	—
CH ₂ -CF ₂	14.12	11.81	—	—
CHF ₂ -CF ₃	13.55	11.92	—	—
CF ₂ -CF ₃	14.08	12.59	—	—

*A. A. Hasanein and F.M.N. Kheiri, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1983, 60, 949. **Ref. 3.

TABLE 5—DIPOLE MOMENTS (Debye)*

Molecule	EHT	Present method	CNDO**	<i>Ab initio</i>	Exptl.
CH ₃ F	7.73	4.63	2.24	2.5	1.85
CH ₂ F ₂	8.34	5.96	2.63	2.69	1.96
CHF ₃	6.74	4.2	2.37	2.18	1.64
CH ₃ -CH ₂ -F	8.49	4.32	—	2.43	—
CH ₃ -CHF ₂	11.35	5.11	—	2.682	—
CH ₂ -CF ₂	12.99	4.55	—	3.501	—
CHF ₂ -CF ₃	7.65	4.31	—	1.012	—

*The molecules CF₄ and CF₂-CF₃ are not included as theoretically they have no dipole moment. **Ref. 20.

One will note that the dipole moment calculation even by an *ab initio* method fails to reproduce the experimental results, and by sheer chance the CNDO values have come out better than the *ab initio* results in some cases. The magnitude of dipole moment value of any individual compound thus becomes less important than the relative order of magnitudes for a series of compounds. Here we see that in each case the relative order of magnitude has been retained so much so that the fact that the molecule CF₂H₂ possessing the lower symmetry (C_{2v}) should possess the highest dipole moment has also been corroborated, though the magnitude for any individual is somewhat greater than the experimental one.

TABLE 6—DISTRIBUTION OF CHARGES IN UNIT OF 10^{-3} ELECTRON

Compd.	Charges on fluorine			Charges on carbon			Charge ratios		
	CNDO	Present method	<i>Ab initio</i>	CNDO	Present method	<i>Ab initio</i>	b/a	b'/a'	b''/a''
	<i>a</i>	<i>a'</i>	<i>a''</i>	<i>b</i>	<i>b'</i>	<i>b''</i>			
CH ₃ F	-189	-66	-15.7	+187	+53	+16.9	0.9	0.8	1.07
CH ₃ F ₂	-21.2	-62	-16.9	26.86	+109	+38.3	1.26	1.8	2.2
CH ₂ F ₂	-195	-58	-17.1	+593	+164	+53.2	3.0	2.83	3.1
C ₂ H ₅ F	-205	-64	—	+215	+53	—	1.04	0.83	—
CH ₃ CF ₃	-216	-58	—	+600	165	—	2.7	2.8	—

^bHehre and Pople, 1970.

Another interesting result is the value for CH₃-CF₃ in which the present method gives a value of 4.55 as against 3.5 in the *ab initio* calculation. This is a molecule where separation of charge is very prominent and molecule possesses a good symmetry. This is quite meaningful in the sense that complete neglect of two electron integrals can get compensated to a large degree where symmetry plays a major role.

Table 6 compares the distribution of charge on some molecules. It is really gratifying to note that although absolute values of charge densities differ but their relative value maintain a consistency. One can not ignore noting that the CNDO values too differ considerably from the *ab initio* values. It is therefore interesting to compare the C/F charge ratios which are shown in the separate columns for different calculations. The last two columns show that the values are very close suggesting that considering the relative separation of charge the present method is of quite importance. This is a considerable success when one considers a large molecule where *ab initio* or CNDO calculations are quite uneconomical considering the computational charges involved and any answer is better²¹ than none. A particular point of interest is the molecule CH₃-CF₃ in which the value of CNDO charge ratio is almost identical with that obtained by the present method. This further corroborates our earlier view that symmetry can somehow compensate the error of approximations made in the present SCEHT.

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